
Operation & Maintenance Manual

for Stormwater Drainage Facilities

SUNNY SKIES SUBDIVISION

(PLAT 25-285)

Chelan County, Washington

Prepared in accordance with:
2024 DOE Stormwater Management Manual for Eastern Washington (SWMMEW)
Pub. No. 24-10-014
Chelan County Storm Drainage Ordinance | Core Element 7 (CE7)

Project Address:	609 American Fruit Road, Wenatchee, WA
Parcel No.:	232017440200
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Certified By:	Justin Wilson, PE
Date:	April 15, 2026
CDI Project #:	25-0092

1.0 Purpose and Scope

This Operation and Maintenance (O&M) Manual establishes the requirements for the ongoing operation, inspection, and maintenance of the permanent stormwater drainage facilities serving the Sunny Skies Subdivision (Plat 25-285), located at 609 American Fruit Road, Wenatchee, Washington (Chelan County Parcel No. 232017440200).

This manual is prepared in compliance with Core Element 7 (CE7: Operation and Maintenance) of the 2024 Stormwater Management Manual for Eastern Washington (SWMMEW), Publication No. 24-10-014, and the Chelan County Storm Drainage Ordinance. Per SWMMEW Section 2.4.7, a written O&M manual is required for all permanent stormwater facilities and must be provided to and accepted by Chelan County prior to project approval.

The maintenance standards presented in Sections 4 and 5 of this manual are derived from SWMMEW Appendix 6-A (BMP Maintenance Tables), specifically:

- Table 6.44 — Maintenance Standards for Infiltration Facilities (Infiltration Pond)
- Table 6.48 — Maintenance Standards for Catch Basins

Compliance with this manual is mandatory. Failure to maintain stormwater facilities as required may result in enforcement action by Chelan County and may result in facility failure, flooding, or groundwater degradation.

2.0 Regulatory Framework

The stormwater management system for Sunny Skies Subdivision has been designed and shall be maintained in accordance with the following regulatory authorities and references:

Authority / Reference	Applicability
2024 SWMMEW (Pub. No. 24-10-014)	Primary stormwater design and O&M guidance manual for Eastern Washington. Maintenance standards per Appendix 6-A; O&M requirements per Section 2.4.7 (CE7).
Chelan County Storm Drainage Ordinance	Local stormwater regulations governing design, construction, and post-construction maintenance of stormwater facilities.
WAC 173-218 — Underground Injection Control (UIC)	The infiltration pond qualifies as a Class V UIC well. Registration and non-endangerment standard compliance may be required. See SWMMEW Chapter 5.
NPDES Phase II Municipal Stormwater Permit (Eastern WA)	Chelan County's permit from WA Dept. of Ecology governing MS4 stormwater programs in eastern Washington.

SWMMEW Section 2.4.7 (CE7: Operation and Maintenance) requires:

- That the project proponent or HOA implement and maintain an O&M program for all permanent stormwater facilities.
- That the O&M manual be included in the Stormwater Site Plan, accepted by Chelan County, and recorded against the property title if required.
- That the responsible party maintain all facilities in proper operating condition and keep maintenance records for inspection by Chelan County upon request.
- That maintenance deficiencies identified during inspection be corrected within a reasonable time period, not to exceed 30 days unless otherwise approved.

3.0 Stormwater Facility Descriptions

The permanent stormwater system for Sunny Skies Subdivision consists of four components: (1) the infiltration pond, (2) catch basin network, (3) underground storm pipe conveyance system, and (4) upstream culvert intercept infrastructure.

3.1 Infiltration Pond (Pond A) — BMP F6.21

Pond A is the primary stormwater control and treatment facility, located within Tract A at the southern end of the property. It is a fully lined native-soil infiltration pond designed per SWMMEW BMP F6.21 (Infiltration Ponds). All runoff collected from the 12-lot subdivision drains to this facility.

Design Parameter	Value / Description
SWMMEW BMP Reference	BMP F6.21 — Infiltration Ponds
Dimensions (W × L × D)	17 ft × 20 ft × 5 ft (Prismatoid, 2:1 side slopes)
Bottom Elevation	991.00 ft
Top of Pond Elevation	996.00 ft
Design Storm	100-Year, 24-Hour (2.60 inches, SCS Type 1A)
Design Infiltration Rate	14.5 in/hr (corrected per SWMMEW Sec. 6.5.4)
Storage Volume (provided)	4,217 cubic feet
Storage Volume (100-yr required)	2,831 cubic feet
100-yr Peak Water Elevation	994.95 ft (3.95 ft depth)
Freeboard to Top of Pond	>1.0 ft (meets SWMMEW minimum)
Drawdown Time	<72 hours (meets SWMMEW SSC-4 requirement)
Depth to Water Table	>160 feet (meets SWMMEW SSC-5 requirement)
Treatment Provided	Pre-treatment + Basic Treatment (SWMMEW Table 5.9)
Overflow Mechanism	Weir overflow; excess routes to natural swale south of site

3.2 Catch Basin Network

Catch basins collect runoff from roadways, sidewalks, and residential lot areas across six drainage sub-basins (B1–B6). Basins are standard precast concrete structures with debris-collecting sumps. They connect to the underground pipe network via 12-inch diameter inlet connections.

3.3 Storm Pipe Conveyance System

The underground storm pipe network (pipes ST-1 through ST-9, all 12-inch diameter) conveys collected runoff from catch basins to Pond A. The system is designed to convey the 100-year storm event without surcharge (HGL verified to remain below rim elevation of all catch basins).

3.4 Upstream Culvert (American Fruit Road)

The existing 12-inch culvert under American Fruit Road, which historically conveyed flows from the SS-9 Basin natural swale (CS-5), has been incorporated into the onsite storm system. It intercepts 100-year upstream flows of 1.27 cfs and routes them into the onsite conveyance network to Pond A.

4.0 Ownership and Maintenance Responsibility

Per SWMMEW Section 2.4.7 (CE7) and Chelan County Code, all stormwater facilities serving Sunny Skies Subdivision shall be owned, operated, and maintained in perpetuity by the Sunny Skies Subdivision Homeowners Association (HOA).

The HOA is responsible for:

- Implementing and maintaining this O&M Manual and all maintenance schedules contained herein.
- Conducting all required inspections at the specified frequencies and maintaining written records.
- Ensuring that all maintenance deficiencies are corrected within 30 days of identification, unless otherwise approved by Chelan County.
- Engaging licensed contractors for maintenance tasks requiring specialized equipment.
- Ensuring no modifications to stormwater facilities are made without prior written approval from Chelan County and a licensed civil engineer.
- Providing Chelan County with access to all stormwater facilities and maintenance records upon request.
- Notifying Chelan County in writing prior to any change in ownership or maintenance responsibility for stormwater facilities.

Transfer of Responsibility: If ownership or maintenance responsibility is transferred to another party, this O&M Manual shall be provided to the successor party and Chelan County shall be notified in writing. The manual shall be recorded against the property title as required by Chelan County.

5.0 Maintenance Standards (Per 2024 SWMMEW Appendix 6-A)

The following maintenance standards are derived directly from the 2024 SWMMEW Appendix 6-A BMP Maintenance Tables and constitute the minimum maintenance requirements for stormwater facilities at this project. Any condition meeting or exceeding a deficiency threshold requires corrective action within 30 days unless the table specifies a different time frame or unless immediate action is required for safety.

5.1 Infiltration Pond (Pond A) — SWMMEW Table 6.44

Source: 2024 SWMMEW Appendix 6-A, Table 6.44 — Maintenance Standards for Infiltration. The deficiencies and corrective actions below are required for BMP F6.21 infiltration ponds and are applied to Pond A.

Deficiency / Condition	Threshold Requiring Maintenance (SWMMEW Table 6.44)	Required Corrective Action
Sediment / Debris Accumulation in Pond	Sediment depth exceeds 6 inches in pond bottom, or debris blocks inlets/outlets	Remove sediment and debris; restore bottom to design grade; dispose of waste per applicable regulations. Inspect inlet/outlet structures after cleaning.
Standing Water (Ponding Beyond 72 Hours)	Water remains in pond more than 72 hours after end of storm event	Identify and remove cause of poor drainage (sediment crust, compaction, root intrusion). Perform scarification or re-grading of pond bottom. Contact engineer if problem persists.
Erosion / Damage to Embankments and Side Slopes	Noticeable erosion on embankments or side slopes; rilling, sloughing, or undercutting present	Re-grade eroded areas; stabilize with compacted native soil; re-seed with approved native grass mix per SWMMEW Appendix 6-B. Install erosion controls if needed.
Vegetation — Mowing and Maintenance	Grass exceeds 18 inches in height; weeds or brush obstruct inspection or access to pond	Mow or cut vegetation to maintain height between 4–12 inches. Do not spray herbicides in or near pond without engineer approval.
Invasive or Noxious Vegetation	Invasive or noxious plant species present within pond or within 10 ft of pond edge	Remove invasive species by hand-pulling or approved mechanical methods. Re-seed bare areas with native grass mix. Do not use herbicides near infiltration area.
Tree or Shrub Growth in Pond Bottom / Side Slopes	Woody vegetation present on side slopes or pond bottom	Remove trees and shrubs; grub stumps. Re-grade if roots have disturbed pond bottom or slopes. Restore to native grass ground cover.
Inlet/Outlet Pipe and Structure Condition	Pipes blocked, offset, cracked, or separated; inlet/outlet structures damaged or deteriorated	Clear blockage immediately. Repair or replace damaged pipe sections. Seal cracks in concrete structures. Contact engineer if significant structural damage is found.
Overflow Weir / Spillway	Weir or spillway blocked, damaged, or showing erosion at base	Clear debris. Repair weir to original design dimensions. Stabilize any scour at weir base with rock riprap or concrete per approved plans.
Unauthorized Fill, Encroachment, or Alteration	Fill material, structures, landscaping, or other encroachments placed within pond tract (Tract A) without approval	Remove encroachment immediately. Restore pond to approved design grade and dimensions. Notify Chelan County.
Fencing / Access Barriers (if provided)	Fencing damaged, down, or missing; access gates inoperable	Repair or replace fencing to original condition. Restore gate hardware and locks as needed.

5.2 Catch Basins — SWMMEW Table 6.48

Source: 2024 SWMMEW Appendix 6-A, Table 6.48 — Maintenance Standards for Catch Basins. All catch basins in the Sunny Skies Subdivision storm system are subject to the following minimum standards.

Deficiency / Condition	Threshold Requiring Maintenance (SWMMEW Table 6.48)	Required Corrective Action
Sediment/Debris in Sump	Sediment or debris in sump exceeds 50% of sump depth, or is within 6 inches of lowest pipe invert	Vacuum-truck or hand-excavate sump. Dispose of solids per applicable regulations (see SWMMEW Appendix 8-B for guidance on street waste solids).
Trash and Debris (General)	Trash, leaves, or debris present in catch basin or blocking grate	Remove trash and debris. Clear grate opening. Inspect downstream pipe for accumulation.
Structural Damage to Frame, Grate, or Lid	Grate or lid is missing, cracked, or unable to support load; frame is bent, misaligned, or settled	Replace missing or broken grate or lid immediately (traffic safety hazard). Reset or replace frame. Adjust to design grade.
Structural Damage to Walls or Base	Cracks wider than 0.5 inch, joint separation, or infiltration of fines through walls	Seal cracks with hydraulic cement or grout. Repair joints. If significant structural deterioration, replace structure.
Inlet/Outlet Pipe Condition	Pipe connections cracked, displaced, or showing infiltration of fines	Re-seat or repair pipe connection. Replace pipe sections as needed. Jet-clean if partially obstructed.
Standing Water in Catch Basin	Water present in sump between storm events (other than design wet sump)	Inspect outlet pipe for blockage. Check downstream system. Clear blockage.
Surface Ponding at Catch Basin Inlet	Standing water on surface around catch basin inlet after storm	Clear grate of debris. If grate is clear, inspect inlet pipe for blockage and address as needed.

5.3 Storm Pipe Network

The following standards apply to the underground storm pipe conveyance system (ST-1 through ST-9). SWMMEW does not provide a separate appendix table for closed-pipe conveyance; the standards below are consistent with SWMMEW guidance for maintaining pipe systems and control structures (Appendix 6-A, Sec. 6.A.6).

Deficiency / Condition	Threshold Requiring Maintenance	Required Corrective Action
Partial or Full Pipe Blockage	Restricted flow, surcharging, or surface overflow along pipe alignment	Jet-clean or rod out pipe. Inspect with CCTV to identify blockage source. Clear and document.
Structural Pipe Failure	Surface subsidence, sinkholes, or depressions along pipe alignment; CCTV shows cracking, offset joints, or root intrusion	Contact engineer. Excavate and repair or replace pipe segment. Do not delay — structural failure can cause surface collapse.
Pipe Outlet Blockage	Outlet pipe to pond inlet blocked or silted	Clear blockage. Inspect outlet connection to pond for damage.

5.4 Upstream Culvert (American Fruit Road)

Deficiency / Condition	Threshold Requiring Maintenance	Required Corrective Action
Culvert Inlet Blockage	Debris, sediment, or vegetation blocking culvert inlet under American Fruit Road	Clear blockage. If roadway is affected, notify Chelan County Public Works immediately.
Structural Damage to Culvert	Pipe cracked, offset, or corroded; roadway settlement above culvert	Notify Chelan County Public Works. Engage engineer and contractor for repair. Do not delay if roadway settlement is present.
Flow Bypassing Culvert / Onsite System	Evidence of surface overflow around culvert or at road edge; flow not entering onsite storm system	Identify bypass location. Clear blockage in culvert and/or onsite connection pipe. Restore flow to intended route.

6.0 Maintenance Schedule Summary

The table below summarizes minimum maintenance frequencies for all facilities. This schedule is the minimum required; more frequent inspection and maintenance may be necessary following significant storm events or if deficiencies are found.

Frequency	Facility	Task	Responsible Party
Monthly (Oct–Apr)	Infiltration Pond (Pond A)	Inspect for standing water, inlet/outlet blockage, erosion	HOA / Designee
Monthly	Catch Basins (all)	Inspect grates for debris; clear surface ponding	HOA / Designee
Semi-annually (Spring & Fall)	Catch Basins (all)	Clean sump if >50% full; inspect structure and pipes	HOA / Contractor
Annually (Fall)	Infiltration Pond (Pond A)	Remove sediment if >6"; mow vegetation; inspect weir; clear inlet/outlet pipes	HOA / Contractor
Annually (Fall)	Upstream Culvert (American Fruit Rd)	Inspect and clear culvert; check flow routing	HOA / Contractor
Every 3 Years	Storm Pipe Network (ST-1 – ST-9)	CCTV inspection of all storm pipes for structural integrity	Licensed Contractor
After Each Storm >1"	All Facilities	Inspect pond, catch basins, and pipe outlets; document findings	HOA / Designee

7.0 Prohibited Activities

The following activities are strictly prohibited within stormwater facility areas (Tract A and all drainage easements) in accordance with SWMMEW Section 5.12 (Prohibited Activities for UIC Wells / Infiltration Facilities) and Chelan County requirements:

- Placing fill, structures, landscaping, or any obstructions within the infiltration pond or drainage easements.
- Altering grading, contours, or dimensions of the infiltration pond from the approved design.
- Paving, compacting, or otherwise reducing the infiltration capacity of the pond bottom or side slopes.

- Discharging non-stormwater flows (irrigation return, pool water, wash water, liquid waste, or any prohibited discharge) to the storm system or pond. Per SWMMEW Section 5.12, only stormwater may be directed to an infiltration facility.
- Applying pesticides, herbicides, or fertilizers within or immediately adjacent to the infiltration pond without engineer approval.
- Dumping yard waste, construction debris, or any solid or hazardous waste in or near any stormwater facility.
- Modifying, removing, bypassing, or replacing any component of the storm system without an approved design and Chelan County permit.
- Any activity that would cause stormwater containing pollutants prohibited under WAC 173-218 (UIC) to be directed to the infiltration pond.

Any prohibited activity resulting in damage or impairment must be remediated at the responsible party's expense. Chelan County may require restoration to original design conditions and may pursue enforcement action.

8.0 Emergency Response Procedures

In the event of a stormwater emergency — including facility failure, flooding, hazardous material spill, structural collapse, or sinkholes — the HOA shall immediately take the following steps:

1. Ensure public safety. Barricade any area posing risk to residents. Do not allow access near collapsed structures or sinkholes.
2. Notify Chelan County Public Works (509-667-6415). Report the nature of the emergency. For hazardous material spills, also call the WA Dept. of Ecology Emergency Spill Response line (1-800-258-5990) immediately.
3. Contact the design engineer. For structural failures or infiltration failure: Complete Design, Inc. — 509.662.3699.
4. Engage a licensed civil contractor to assess and address the failure. Do not attempt repairs to structural pipe failures, embankment failures, or pond structure damage without engineering oversight.
5. Document all damage. Photograph all conditions. Prepare a written incident report for the HOA maintenance log and Chelan County records.
6. Obtain required permits before beginning restoration work. Restore all facilities to original approved design specifications.

9.0 Key Contacts

Entity	Contact / Notes	Phone
Complete Design, Inc. (Design Engineer)	353 Malaga Alcoa Hwy, Suite 3, Wenatchee, WA info@completedesign.cc	509.662.3699
Justin Wilson, PE (Engineer of Record)	CDI Project #25-0092	509.662.3699
Chelan County Planning & Development Services	Stormwater permits, plan review, enforcement	509-667-6225
Chelan County Public Works	Roadway / culvert emergencies, downstream coordination	509-667-6415
WA Dept. of Ecology — Eastern Region	Stormwater permit compliance, UIC registration	509-329-3400
WA Dept. of Ecology — Emergency Spill Response	24-hour hazardous materials spill hotline	1-800-258-5990
Wenatchee Reclamation District (WRD)	Downstream drainage coordination	Contact via Chelan County

10.0 Summary and Certification

This Operation and Maintenance Manual establishes the minimum requirements for the inspection and maintenance of stormwater drainage facilities serving Sunny Skies Subdivision (Plat 25-285), in compliance with Core Element 7 of the 2024 SWMMEW and Chelan County’s Storm Drainage Ordinance.

The maintenance standards in Section 5 are drawn directly from SWMMEW Appendix 6-A (Tables 6.44 and 6.48) and govern both the infiltration pond and catch basin network. When properly maintained in accordance with this manual, the stormwater system will provide effective runoff control and water quality treatment through the 100-year design event with no adverse impact to downstream drainage or groundwater quality.

The Homeowners Association is responsible for ensuring all maintenance is performed as specified herein, records are kept for a minimum of 5 years, and Chelan County is notified of any ownership transfer. Questions should be directed to Complete Design, Inc. at 509.662.3699.

— End of O&M Manual Body —

ANNUAL INSPECTION CHECKLIST

Sunny Skies Subdivision (Plat 25-285) — Stormwater Drainage Facilities
Per 2024 SWMMEW Appendix 6-A (Tables 6.44 & 6.48) and Chelan County Storm Drainage Ordinance

Date of Inspection:		Inspector Name:	
Weather Conditions:		Days Since Last Storm:	

A. INFILTRATION POND (Pond A) — Tract A, South End of Property

Reference: SWMMEW Appendix 6-A, Table 6.44 — Maintenance Standards for Infiltration

#	Inspection Item (SWMMEW Table 6.44)	Acceptable Condition / Threshold	Findings / Action Taken
1	No standing water present in pond	Pond drains within 72 hours of storm end (SWMMEW SSC-4)	
2	Sediment depth in pond bottom	Sediment < 6 inches deep; does not block inlet/outlet	
3	Pond side slopes — erosion and stability	No rilling, sloughing, or undercutting of slopes	
4	Vegetation condition — mowing and invasives	Grass 4–12 inches; no invasive or noxious species present	
5	Tree/shrub growth on side slopes or bottom	No woody vegetation on slopes or bottom	
6	Inlet pipes — clear and undamaged	Pipes fully open; no cracks, displacement, or separation	
7	Outlet connections and pond inlet structure	Connections clear and structurally intact	
8	Overflow weir — clear and structurally sound	Weir free of debris; no structural damage or scour	
9	No unauthorized fill or encroachments in Tract A	Tract A maintained exclusively as stormwater facility	
10	Fencing / access markers (if provided)	Markers or fencing intact and visible	

B. CATCH BASINS — All Basins in the Subdivision

Reference: SWMMEW Appendix 6-A, Table 6.48 — Maintenance Standards for Catch Basins

#	Inspection Item (SWMMEW Table 6.48)	Acceptable Condition / Threshold	Findings / Action Taken
1	Grate and lid — present, intact, and secure	No missing, broken, or unsecured grates/lids	
2	Sump — sediment and debris level	Sump less than 50% full; sediment >6" below pipe invert	

#	Inspection Item (SWMMEW Table 6.48)	Acceptable Condition / Threshold	Findings / Action Taken
3	Structural condition — walls and base	No cracks wider than 0.5 inch; no joint separation	
4	Inlet/outlet pipe connections — condition	Pipes fully seated; no cracks, displacement, or infiltration	
5	No surface ponding around catch basin inlet	No standing water at grate surface after storm clears	

C. STORM PIPES & UPSTREAM CULVERT

#	Inspection Item	Acceptable Condition / Threshold	Findings / Action Taken
1	All pipe outlets clear and unobstructed	No blockage or debris at any outlet end	
2	No surface subsidence along pipe alignment	No depressions or settlement visible above pipes	
3	No sinkholes or unusual ponding above pipes	Surface consistent with surroundings	
4	Upstream culvert (American Fruit Road) — inlet clear	No debris or sediment blocking inlet	
5	Flow entering onsite system at culvert — not bypassing	No evidence of surface overflow around culvert	

<p>Overall Facility Status:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> All facilities in acceptable condition</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Deficiencies noted — corrective action required</p>	<p>Inspector Signature:</p> <p>_____</p> <p>Date: _____</p>
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Deficiencies must be corrected within 30 days. Attach additional sheets if needed. Retain completed checklists for a minimum of 5 years. Make available to Chelan County upon request.

